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Work Report – European Project on Oncogenomics Education in Molecular Tumour Boards

1. Executive Summary

This report outlines the work undertaken as part of WP13 Task 2.1 of the European project on educational advancement in oncogenomics within Molecular Tumour Boards (MTBs). The objective of this work was to identify and understand the educational needs, barriers, and challenges faced by healthcare professionals (HCPs) involved in MTBs. A mixed-methods approach was employed, comprising a rapid review of the literature, a Delphi study for expert consensus, and a Europe-wide survey. The outputs from this work package will serve as the foundation for developing evidence-based, targeted educational interventions to build genomic literacy and support the integration of precision oncology across clinical settings in Europe.

2. Objectives

- To systematically identify knowledge gaps and training needs in oncogenomics among healthcare professionals participating in MTBs
- To reach consensus on educational priorities and challenges using a Delphi method
- To validate and expand findings through a structured survey
- To inform the development of targeted educational materials for MTBs

3. Methods

3.1 Rapid Review

The rapid review followed PRISMA principles adapted for time-sensitive synthesis.

Databases: PubMed and Scopus

Search Date: February 2, 2023

Inclusion Criteria:

- Studies published in English between January 1, 2018 and January 1, 2023
- Studies involving HCPs participating in or eligible for MTBs (e.g., oncologists, pathologists, geneticists)
- Studies addressing educational needs, training gaps, challenges in genomics or oncogenomics
- Quantitative, qualitative, or mixed-methods

Exclusion Criteria:

- Opinion pieces, conference abstracts, editorials, or papers not involving HCPs

Selection Process:

- 5,483 articles retrieved; 1,842 duplicates removed

- 3,441 records screened by title and abstract
- 107 full-text articles reviewed
- 35 primary studies and 30 review articles included

Data Analysis:

Thematic analysis was used to synthesize findings.

3.2 Delphi Study

A Delphi technique was conducted to refine and prioritize items identified in the rapid review.

Participants: 15 experts (clinicians, educators, geneticists, researchers)

Rounds: 3 (Round 1: 14 respondents; Round 2: 12 respondents; Round 3: 10 respondents)

Process:

- 93 items rated across domains: education, communication, clinical practice, and diagnosis
- A 9-point Likert scale was used to assess importance
- Items with $\geq 75\%$ agreement in the 7–9 range were considered consensus
- Participants could propose new items in Round 1

3.3 Survey

A survey was developed and disseminated to oncology and genetics professionals across Europe to validate the identified themes and gain further insights.

Platform: EU Survey

Respondents: 34

Consent Rate: 88.24%

Survey Content: Demographics, educational experience, communication skills, clinical practice, and barriers

4. Results

4.1 Rapid Review

Three major themes emerged regarding educational needs:

Genomic Education

- Strong demand for post-residency training in oncogenomics
- Knowledge gaps in hereditary cancer, tissue handling, and the distinction between somatic and germline mutations
- Preferences for flexible learning formats, including online courses and podcasts

Communication Skills

- Inadequate preparation for discussing complex genomic data

- Communication barriers with patients of low literacy or diverse cultural backgrounds
- Need for skills in delivering sensitive results and navigating ethical issues

Application to Clinical Practice

- Limited confidence in test interpretation and decision-making
- Inconsistent referral protocols and multidisciplinary collaboration
- Barriers included a lack of standardized procedures and institutional support

4.2 Delphi Study

Consensus was reached on several critical educational priorities:

Education:

- Genomic testing, targeted therapies, somatic vs germline distinctions
- Use of bioinformatic tools such as OncoKB and cbioPortal
- National guidelines, variant classification standards, and SOP comprehension

Communication:

- Explaining results clearly to patients and families
- Effective teamwork in interdisciplinary settings
- Awareness of legal and ethical responsibilities

Clinical Practice:

- Utilizing genomic findings to inform treatment plans
- Strengthening referral systems and case tracking
- Introducing and applying new diagnostic technologies

Diagnosis:

- Recognition of hereditary syndromes (HBOC, Lynch, LFS, MEN, VHL, etc.)
- Understanding polygenic risk scores and reproductive options (e.g., PGD)

4.3 Survey Results

Demographics:

- 70.59% female specialists
- 47% employed in academic institutions
- Most respondents had over six years of professional experience

Training History:

- 64.7% received formal lectures in genomics
- 67.6% participated in workshops

- 38.2% lacked any training in genomic communication

Identified Gaps:

- Pharmacogenomics (56%), interpretation tools (47%), and ethical guidelines (41%)

Preferred Learning Formats:

- Self-guided reading (53%)
- Structured academic courses (50%)
- Online learning modules (41%)

Clinical Challenges:

- Absence of SOPs and consistent interdisciplinary communication
- Difficulty in selecting and applying the right genomic tests

Communication Barriers:

- Cultural and literacy issues among patients
- Limited integration between clinicians and diagnosticians
- Ethical complexity in discussing results

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study reveals significant deficits in oncogenomics education and systemic issues hampering the effective incorporation of genomic data into clinical practice. Through triangulated methods—literature review, expert consensus, and practitioner feedback—a comprehensive understanding of current limitations was established.

Recommendations include:

- Development of flexible, role-specific training modules
- Prioritization of communication strategies and ethical competency
- Institutional frameworks for SOP adoption and interdisciplinary training
- Ongoing engagement with stakeholders to ensure alignment with clinical needs

6. Next Steps

In alignment with the identified needs, a two-day online workshop on Oncogenomics and Precision Medicine was held on Friday, 28 February 2025 and Friday, 7 March 2025. The structure of the course is available for review, and each session's content is accessible online to ensure continued dissemination and learning impact.

7. Appendices

Appendix A. Agenda of the Online Workshop

Appendix B. PRISMA Flow Chart of Study Selection (Rapid Review)

Appendix C. Full List of Items Reaching Consensus in Delphi Study

Appendix D. Survey Questionnaire and Response Summary

Appendix A. Agenda of the Online Workshop

Agenda 1

Realizing Precision Oncology: Perspectives from Different Stakeholders

- **Torsten Haferlach** – *Role of AI in the Diagnostics of Leukemia*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15145731](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15145731)
- **Maria Nomikou** – *Patients*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15144886](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15144886)

Innovative Informatics and Data Sharing Solutions for Oncogenomics

- **Fotis Psomopoulos** – *Challenges and Opportunities of AI in Bio-data*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15145391](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15145391)
- **Thomas Chatzinikolaou** – *Impact of Real-World Data for Precision Cancer Medicine*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15146004](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15146004)

International Perspectives on Precision Oncology

- **Kostas Stamatopoulos** – *Precision Oncology in Greece: Solving the Unsolved?*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15146280](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15146280)
- **Celia Dupain** – *Molecular Tumor Board and French Genomic Medicine: 2025 Initiative*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15146493](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15146493)

Precision Medicine in Action: Best Practice Examples

- **Tomasz Stoklosa** – *Implementing Genomic Sequencing for Diagnostics and MRD Monitoring*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15146710](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15146710)
- **Torsten Haferlach** – *Comprehensive Genomic Profiling for Clinical Decision-Making*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15146961](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15146961)

Precision Oncology: Ethical Dimensions

- **Christina Karamanidou** – *Communication of Genetic Results to Patients' Relatives*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147099](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147099)

- **Liis Leitsalu** – *Patient Participation and Consent Models*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15182260](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15182260)

Agenda 2

Precision Oncology: Where Do We Stand Now?

- **Elena Fountzila** – *Solid Tumors and Hereditary Cancer Syndromes*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147360)

Challenges in Cancer Genomics and Clinical Reporting

- **Giovanni Tonon** – *Harnessing Data to Improve Cancer Treatment*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147409](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147409)
- **Jolie De Bien** – *Single Cell Sequencing in Hematology*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147462](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147462)

International Perspectives on Precision Oncology

- **Giovanni Tonon** – *A Federated Learning System for Precision Oncology in Europe: DigiONE*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147507](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147507)
- **Jesus Maria Hernandez Rivas** – *Precision in Spain*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147542](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147542)

Precision Oncology Beyond Genomics

- **Pantelis Natsiavas** – *Drug Repurposing in Precision Oncology*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147613](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147613)
- **Junyan Lu** – *Multi-Omics Profiling Based Precision Cancer Medicine*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147674](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147674)

International Perspectives on Precision Oncology (continued)

- **Sarka Pospisilova** – *Czech Republic*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147709](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147709)
- **Mateja Krajc** – *The Development of the Clinical Pathways for Genetic Testing in Slovenia*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147737](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147737)
- **Edjo Anders** – *Sweden*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147786](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147786)

Health Economic Evaluation of Precision Oncology

- **Kostas Athanasakis** - *Value Assessment Frameworks*
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15147819](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15147819)

Appendix B. PRISMA Flow Chart of Study Selection (Rapid Review)

*Report on a Rapid Review on Identifying
Challenges and Educational Needs of Molecular
Tumour Boards Members in Oncogenomics.*

Introduction

Oncology is a fast-growing field, with the inherent complexity of cancer care, the involvement of multidisciplinary care teams, and health care delivery to diverse health literacy levels and cultural backgrounds (Sullivan et al., 2017). Clinical genomic testing is becoming increasingly integrated into oncology practice, with oncologists collaborating with genome scientists and other medical practitioners to analyse and evaluate genomic sequencing data for potential cancer treatments (Chow-White et al., 2017). It is anticipated that within the next ten years, the developments in genomic medicine will completely reshape every aspect of the diagnostic approaches, prevention strategies and treatment of cancer patients, raising survival rates and enhancing patient outcomes (Seed et al., 2021). To maintain competency and deliver high-quality medical care, medical experts need to highly engage and stay up-to-date with the advances in genomic research, as these have become increasingly important in guiding treatment options (Chakravarty et al., 2017).

Furthermore, substantial knowledge gaps among oncologists have been identified, underscoring the need for consultants and trainees to receive better formal training in cancer genomics. This will allow an effective preparation for applying advancements in clinical practice and to confidently embrace genetic mainstreaming, meaning the integration of genetic information and genetic testing into routine healthcare and medical practice. Adequate training will ensure that genetic knowledge and testing are accessible, well apprehended and used effectively to improve patient care and treatment outcomes (Tutika et al., 2023).

Advancements in genomic sequencing technologies have enabled medical practitioners to diagnose, analyze, and treat cancer on an individual patient's genome composition. However, the translation of genomic services into clinical care poses a significant challenge due to the rapid expansion of genomic science and the generation of novel information that can create uncertainty and doubt among clinicians (Berg et al., 2011; Bombard et al., 2015). To address this challenge, it is important to assess the current level of knowledge in cancer clinical genomics among physicians, particularly in understanding the genetic variations among individual patients and tumours. Moreover, the importance of enhancing genomic literacy among medical professionals, particularly medical oncologists, working in remote practice locations, through educational interventions is further emphasized (Chow-White et al., 2017).

In Europe, the research on educational gaps and needs of oncologists and other members of the care team is limited, which can hinder the integration of genomics into clinical oncology practice (Sassano et al., 2021). Identifying these gaps is crucial for ensuring high-quality cancer care. Evidence-based information on how to handle various cancer types is required, as are updates on new diagnostic tools and therapeutic approaches. Participating in tumour boards, where a diverse group of healthcare professionals (HCP) discusses complex cases, is critical for oncologists to gain insight and work collaboratively (Melas et al., 2020). Furthermore, peer panels may enhance knowledge through the sharing of experiences. In addition, self-directed learning by attending medical conferences, reading relevant articles and engaging in online discussions is also imperative for oncologists to stay current with new research findings and advances in cancer treatment. However, there are limited studies surveying a range of specialities working in oncology or related fields.

Hence, we conducted a rapid review in an attempt to offer a comprehensive analysis of the current level of genetic literacy among HCPs in oncology in European registries. Additionally, this review aims to identify possible interventions and strategies to improve genomic literacy in oncology. The results of this research will provide a detailed understanding of physicians' knowledge in the field and will be used in order to implement practical solutions to improve clinical genomics education.

Methods

The present rapid review aimed to identify the challenges and educational needs of Molecular Tumour Boards (MTB) members in oncogenomics.

Selection Criteria

The included studies had to comprise HCP working in MTB; namely, medical oncologists, hematologists, pathologists, geneticists, molecular biologists, biostatisticians, computational biologists (bioinformaticians), pharmacists, radiologists, and nurses. The articles reviewed aimed at exploring the MTB professionals education needs, knowledge gaps or understanding around oncogenomics and/or challenges in the same area. Moreover, quantitative, qualitative and review studies were included in the review, published in English from 1 January 2018 to 1 January 2023.

Studies were excluded if they included non-professional personnel or individuals without relevant expertise, or if they did not present results of HCPs as a subgroup. Studies were similarly excluded if they were presenting curricula or

guidelines. Lastly, multiple reports of the same study, e.g. study protocols, conference abstracts, opinion papers, correspondence, perspectives, letters, or editorials were excluded.

Information Sources and Search Strategy

All articles were retrieved on February 2, 2023, from PubMed and Scopus.

The following algorithm was used in aforementioned databases:

```
((((Cancer*[Title/Abstract] OR oncolog*[Title/Abstract] OR
malignan*[Title/Abstract] OR Tumor*[Title/Abstract] OR Tumour*[Title/Abstract]
OR Neopl*[Title/Abstract]) AND (Genetic*[Title/Abstract] OR
genom*[Title/Abstract] OR oncogenomic*[Title/Abstract] OR next generation
sequencing[Title/Abstract] OR NGS[Title/Abstract] OR molecular tumour
board*[Title/Abstract] OR MTB[Title/Abstract] OR personalized
medicine[Title/Abstract] OR therapeutic opportunit*[Title/Abstract] OR target*
therapy[Title/Abstract] OR precision oncology[Title/Abstract] OR molecular
diagnosis[Title/Abstract] OR molecular diagnostic*[Title/Abstract] OR actionable
mutation*[Title/Abstract] OR off-label[Title/Abstract] OR off label[Title/Abstract]
OR genomic profil*[Title/Abstract] OR tumor DNA[Title/Abstract] OR tumour
DNA[Title/Abstract])) AND (Healthcare professional*[Title/Abstract] OR
Healthcare provider*[Title/Abstract] OR Healthcare personnel*[Title/Abstract] OR
Healthcare worker*[Title/Abstract] OR healthcare staff*[Title/Abstract] OR
Physician*[Title/Abstract] OR Practitioner*[Title/Abstract] OR Nurs*[Title/Abstract]
OR Doctor*[Title/Abstract] OR Oncologist*[Title/Abstract] OR
Hematologist*[Title/Abstract] OR Pathologist*[Title/Abstract] OR
Geneticist*[Title/Abstract] OR Biologist*[Title/Abstract] OR
Pharmacist*[Title/Abstract] OR Radiologist*[Title/Abstract] OR
professional*[Title/Abstract])) AND (Know*[Title/Abstract] OR
understand*[Title/Abstract] OR education*[Title/Abstract] OR teach*[Title/Abstract]
OR training[Title/Abstract] OR skill*[Title/Abstract] OR barrier*[Title/Abstract] OR
Challeng*[Title/Abstract] OR obstacle*[Title/Abstract] OR
impediment*[Title/Abstract] OR difficult*[Title/Abstract] OR
problem*[Title/Abstract] OR limitation*[Title/Abstract] OR
hindrance[Title/Abstract])
```

Selection Process

Studies retrieved from the electronic searches were imported into Zotero (<https://www.zotero.org/>) and duplicate studies automatically merged (according to the title, DOI, ISBN) using the appropriate extension. Then, the studies were imported into Rayyan (<https://www.rayyan.ai/>); in case of any further duplicates identified, these were reviewed manually to assess whether they are true duplicates or not. Following this, and to assess the accuracy of the selection process, a 5% sample of the retrieved articles was reviewed (title and abstract) by two independent researchers (clinical psychologist and medical doctor). The remaining 95% of the articles were screened (title and abstract) by one of two researchers. Following this, the full texts of the selected articles were retrieved. The full texts of these studies were reviewed by one of the researchers to retrieve the relevant information from them. Any uncertainties were discussed between the two researchers and, if needed, a third researcher offered their insights to reach a consensus.

Synthesis of Data

The retrieved data were synthesized using qualitative methodology. Specifically, the thematic analysis allowed for patterns and themes of the literature concerning the educational needs and the challenges of professionals to emerge. The information collected from the included articles was related to methodology (study type, country), participants (total sample size, specialization of participants, gender, age), and results (educational needs, challenges).

Results

This section provides the main findings of this rapid review. Regarding the studies selected for analysis, the following gaps and challenges were identified:

Study selection

The search strategy retrieved a total of 5483 articles. Of these, 1842 were removed as they were duplicates. A total of 3441 records were screened by two authors for their eligibility on the title and the abstract. Out of these, 107 studies and 34 reviews were selected for full-text review and those that did not meet the criteria were excluded. Finally, a total of 35 studies and 30 reviews were included.

Study characteristics

Thirty-five studies met the eligibility criteria. They were published between 2018 and 2023 across 9 countries. Sixteen studies were conducted in the USA, 5 in Australia, 5 in the Netherlands, 4 in Canada, 1 in Japan, 1 in Malaysia, 1 in Italy, 1 in Ireland, and 1 in France. Additionally, 30 reviews meeting the inclusion criteria were included. The

publication dates ranged between 2018 and 2022 and the reviews originated from groups in Australia, , Europe (including United Kingdom, Belgium, Switzerland, Italy, and France), Cyprus, Canada, USA, Singapore, and India.

Methodological characteristics

Of the included studies, 24 used quantitative methodology, 8 qualitative, while 3 studies chose mixed-methods (qualitative and quantitative).

Participants' characteristics

The mean age of participants ranged from 42.9 to 54.8. Articles included both male and female participants, although no articles provided information on percentages.

Results of Synthesis

Three distinct themes emerged regarding the educational needs of MTB members in oncogenomics.

Need for genomics education

The HCPs' answers highlighted an urgent need for not only active continuing education on oncogenomics after the completion of the residency (Loeb et al., 2021), but also for specialized knowledge regarding genetics/genomics. Specifically, the topics that should be covered concern tissue sampling (e.g., sampling technique and tissue handling methods), fixation techniques (Zer et al., 2018) and more education regarding hereditary cancer (e.g., its characteristics; Matsumoto et al., 2022; Medendorp et al., 2020). Moreover, the topics that require more education concern the specificities of tumour and the selection procedure of germline testing (Selvarajah et al., 2022), including the difference between germline and somatic tests, and indications for testing in the guidelines (Loeb et al., 2021). Besides these, the rapid review revealed the demand for educational tools and resources, preferably through online material and podcasts (Weipert et al., 2018; Smit et al., 2021; Hall et al., 2021), which could assist health professionals to better comprehend new information. Moreover, embracing new technologies will assist MTB members to offer individualized therapies and "state-of-the-art care" (Vetsch et al., 2019).

Communication skills

Education should also include ways to strengthen communication skills and to communicate effectively genetic information. HCPs mentioned that they did not feel confident with patients with low health literacy or immigrant background, as they faced challenges in identifying the insufficient understanding of healthcare information. This lack of recognition undermined their self-efficacy in effective communication. For

example, a referral for genetic testing is not always adequately discussed with patients with limited health literacy (van der Giessen et al., 2018). Also, HCPs felt uncertain about explaining and communicating genomic results (McGill et al., 2020; Hall et al., 2021; Medendorp et al., 2020). MTB members should also have a good understanding of the Genetic Non-Discrimination Act (GNDA) so that they can provide reassurance to patients who have fears about how their test results might be used (Selvarajah et al., 2022).

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the studies of the rapid review.

Education in using genomics in clinical practice

The findings of the rapid review indicate that MTB members do not feel confident or sufficiently competent to make decisions about whether to order polygenic testing and/or incorporate it into their clinical practice (Zer et al., 2018; Smit et al., 2021). For instance, some cancer genetics professionals and oncologists acknowledged that oncologists often order genetic testing for inherited risk directly rather than refer

patients to specialized genetic services (Korngiebel et al., 2019). Moreover, HCPs were not confident in interpreting genetic test results (Underhill et al., 2020; McGill et al., 2020; Korngiebel et al., 2019; Selvarajah et al., 2022; Hall et al., 2021) and making treatment recommendations (McGill et al., 2020; Gray et al., 2018) due to the acknowledged need for education and training in this topic. Another topic highlighted is the critical need for professionals to be aware of the referral criteria (Loeb et al., 2021; Underhill et al., 2020; Gietel-Habets et al., 2018) and how to manage the volume and the urgency of referrals for germline testing (Selvarajah et al., 2022).

Four distinct themes emerged for the challenges/barriers in meeting the educational needs of MTB members in oncogenomics.

Educational challenges/gaps

Through the rapid review, some educational gaps were also observed. One of them is the genetic and risk identification illiteracy, as some HCPs noted different estimations on risk identification of e.g. targetable Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) mutations (Muñoz-Antonia et al., 2019) and uncertainty around the roles and responsibilities of HCPs managing e.g. high-risk women around risk-reducing bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy (RRBSO; Hickey et al., 2020). Another issue concerns the limited baseline knowledge and/or experience regarding genetics/genomics (Loeb et al., 2021). Specifically, there is uncertainty in interpreting results, especially in atypical cases (Korngiebel et al., 2019), in managing adverse outcomes (Smit et al., 2021) and proceeding further with therapies (Petrilo et al., 2022), for instance, in diagnosing and treating Li-Fraumeni Syndrome (LFS) (Bakhuizen et al., 2019). In addition, HCPs were uncertain when to ask for TP53 (Bakhuizen et al., 2019) and TGP testing (Hall et al., 2021), and they lack the knowledge on handling high-risk cases for decision-making, leading to incorrect risk estimation (Smit et al., 2021).

Communicational challenges

Gaps in HCPs' education are noted in communicating genomic results, as they cannot handle patients' disinterest (Czekalski et al., 2022). In some cases, they do not maintain privacy and share information with third parties (e.g., family members; Anderson et al., 2021). In others, they are misinterpreting treatment options and they do not know how to manage family disputes (Spees et al., 2021; Bakhuizen et al., 2019; Young et al., 2019). Moreover, inadequate information on the availability of low and no-cost options (Douglas et al., 2022), handling patients diagnosed at a young age (Bakhuizen et al.,

2019), involving patients/families in the decision-making process for Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) (Paller et al., 2019; Spees et al., 2021; Selvarajah et al., 2022; O'Neill et al., 2018).

Clinical practice barriers and challenges

Challenges were noted in clinical practice. For example, applying knowledge of interpreting genomic results in real-life (e.g., multigene cancer test panels; Korngiebel et al., 2019; Selvarajah et al., 2022; Hall et al., 2021); difficulty in making treatment recommendations after interpreting the genomic results of a particular patient (McGill et al., 2020; Gray et al., 2018); lack of cooperation among the multidisciplinary team members (e.g., misinterpretation of results by non-genetic specialists, delays in diagnosis; De Giglio et al., 2023); lack of established procedures (e.g. referral protocol, limited testing guidelines and protocols; Underhill et al., 2020; De Giglio et al., 2023; Selvarajah et al., 2022; Dicks et al., 2019); and, even racial discrimination (e.g., screening, costs/insurance; Ademuyiwa et al., 2021).

Limited resources

The rapid review revealed a lack of resources. This includes a lack of educational materials (Loeb et al., 2021; Spees et al., 2021; Underhill et al., 2020) and training (McHugh et al., 2022; Dick et al., 2021; Loeb et al., 2021). Moreover, there was a distinct shortage of genetic counsellors (De Simone et al., 2021; Korngiebel et al., 2019) leading to lack of time for trained professionals (Gleeson et al., 2020; Paller et al., 2019) and sometimes even to a lack of space and clinic rooms (Paller et al., 2019). Lastly, a push to promote population-based screening on a routine basis has been highlighted but cannot be implemented due to limited resources (De Simone et al., 2021). Further, more education is needed in treatment recommendations and referral processes.

Results of reviews synthesis

The following section presents the principal outcomes obtained from the rapid review of review studies, conducted herein.

Genomics literacy

Risk assessment and management of patients with an inherited cancer predisposition present formidable challenges within the domain of oncogenomics (Giri et al., 2022; Price et al., 2020; Starkings et al., 2020; Young et al., 2020). Improved family-history-taking and risk assessment strategies are needed to accurately identify individuals at

higher risk (Hoxhaj et al., 2021). Additionally, addressing the potential consequences of testing is crucial, including the impact on risk assessment, prevention strategies, patient-doctor communication, and treatment decision support. Moreover, the integration of genetic testing requires consideration of ethical, legal, and psychosocial aspects to ensure appropriate support and counselling (Ashbury et al., 2021; Paul et al., 2018).

Genomic testing and counselling in the field of oncogenomics face several challenges and barriers that need to be addressed for effective implementation. Limited awareness and utilization of existing and new genomic technologies hinder the integration of advanced tools for accurate diagnosis and treatment selection (Ha et al., 2018). In addition, the interpretation of results can be challenging, requiring specialized training and expertise (Davis et al., 2018; El Saghir et al. 2021). Another major challenge concerns the lack of comprehensive educational resources, including courses, and online or other resources, that cover the latest developments in molecular oncology (Morgan et al., 2020; Verma et al. 2019). Many healthcare professionals also lack the necessary training and expertise to interpret genomic testing results, which can limit the effectiveness of cancer treatments and management (Ha et al., 2018). Moreover, the translation of cancer genomics research into clinical practice is often limited or varied, impeding the widespread application of genomic knowledge (Chiang et al., 2020; Ha et al., 2018; Hoxhaj et al. 2021; Kurnat-Thoma et al., 2020; Malone et al., 2020; Morgan et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2021; Schmid et al., 2022; Verma et al., 2019; Vetsch et al., 2019). Another challenge lies in accurately distinguishing between different types of mutations, including somatic versus germline mutations (Bacher et al., 2018; Ha et al., 2018), which is essential for precise diagnosis and treatment decisions. Additionally, genetic-guided patient selection for precision medicine testing (Gkolfinopoulos et al., 2018; Janssens et al., 2018) requires comprehensive understanding and expertise to effectively identify patients who can benefit from targeted therapies based on their genetic profiles. Limited knowledge of genetic counselling (Morgan et al., 2020; Verma et al., 2019; Young et al., 2020) further adds to these challenges, emphasizing the need for healthcare professionals to enhance their understanding of this critical aspect. Moreover, time constraints and turnaround time for results may negatively impact the ordering of genetic tests (Ashbury et al., 2021; Paul et al., 2018). Equally important, when applying genetic testing, ethical considerations including informed consent,

privacy issues, genetic discrimination risk, and psychosocial impact should be taken into consideration (Kurnat-Thoma et al., 2020).

Implementation challenges

Communication challenges in oncogenomics present significant barriers that need to be addressed for effective patient care. These challenges include communicating outcomes to younger individuals, since many factors need to be addressed and taken into consideration in order to make informed decisions, for example, the cognitive capacity of the individual, and also the emerging emotions of guilt and anxiety in family members (Young et al., 2020). Communicating evidence-based hereditary risk information to family members is also a challenge for HCPs. Additionally, there is a lack of communication regarding prognosis-related information, hindering patients' understanding of their condition and treatment options (LeBlanc et al., 2018). Opposing genetic testing decisions within families further complicate decision-making processes by interfering with the treatment plan, thus, strategies to navigate differing perspectives are required (El Saghir et al., 2021; Paul et al., 2018; Starkings et al., 2020; Young et al., 2020). Furthermore, effective communication of risk-based information and test results is essential for patients and their relatives to comprehend and make informed decisions (Ashbury et al., 2021; Hoxhaj et al., 2021; LeBlanc et al., 2018; Paul et al., 2018; Rahman et al., 2021; Starkings et al., 2020; Young et al., 2020). Moreover, nursing staff specializing in oncology require training to effectively identify and manage the risk of patient non-adherence, while also nurturing collaborative relationships with their patients (Rahman et al., 2021; El Saghir et al., 2021; Saigal et al., 2018). Empathic communication approaches are vital in addressing emotional concerns and supporting patients throughout their journey.

The lack of established guidelines and procedural frameworks in molecular oncology presents significant challenges and barriers that impede progress in the field. These include limitations in next generation sequencing (NGS) technology, testing capabilities, or lack of services that provide testing, (Bacher et al., 2018; Bontoux et al., 2022; Kurnat-Thoma et al., 2020; Normanno et al., 2022). In addition, high costs for health care systems, organizational constraints and policies affecting interdisciplinary approaches, implementation challenges of newly discovered precision medicines (Ashbury et al., 2021; Bacher et al., Brown et al., 2020; 2018; Davis et al., 2018;

Edelman et al., 2019; Fountzilias et al., 2018; Malone et al., 2020; Pail et al., 2018; Rahman et al., 2021; Vetsch et al., 2019), and limited public awareness of genetic testing (Ha et al., 2018) may hinder the implementation of informed decision-making in cancer care.

Cultural and accessibility constraints render the application of genetics and oncogenomics difficult, stemming from limited access to genetic services (Morgan et al., 2020), challenges in genetic counselling (El Saghir et al., 2021; Paul et al., 2018; Verma et al., 2019), concerns for the cultural stigma associated with genetic mutations among families (El Saghir et al., 2021), limitations in infrastructure and expertise (El Saghir et al., 2021; Normanno et al., 2022; Rahman et al., 2021; Saigal et al., 2018), and regional disparities in practice (Ha et al., 2018). Although genomic testing is becoming increasingly available, it is not yet widely accessible, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Overcoming these barriers is crucial to ensure equitable access, improve counselling practices, address cultural misconceptions, enhance infrastructure and expertise, and promote regional equity. Identifying and addressing these challenges is necessary to bridge the gaps in utilising genomics and oncogenomics, facilitating their integration into healthcare systems and promoting personalized care for diverse populations.

Conclusion

The current rapid review underscores the critical challenges in the implementation of oncogenomics. Major gaps and challenges were found in the areas of education, communication and clinical practice of MTB. These ranged from basic (e.g., what is a biomarker) to more advanced (e.g., making treatment recommendations based on reading oncogenomic test results). These findings will be fed into the survey and will further extend the gap analysis of education. In turn these findings will dictate the nature of the courses, in terms of content, which should be offered to HCPs according to their preferences.

Furthermore, despite the fact that most of the identified studies originated from outside Europe, global collaboration is essential, as cancer research and genomics advancements are international endeavours. The shared burden of cancer necessitates Europe's attention to these challenges, allowing for knowledge exchange and comprehensive understanding. By leveraging lessons learned from other countries, Europe can expedite progress and equip healthcare professionals with the necessary

knowledge and skills. To effectively address these challenges and enhance healthcare practices, a multifaceted approach is required. The recommended solutions include the implementation of comprehensive educational programs, fostering collaboration among institutions, establishing supportive policies and incentives, and raising awareness among healthcare professionals. By adopting these measures, Europe can bridge the educational divide, promote genomic literacy, and ultimately improve patient outcomes in cancer care. It is imperative for policymakers, educational institutions, and healthcare stakeholders to work together in implementing these solutions to create a robust and well-informed healthcare workforce capable of delivering high-quality, genomic-driven cancer care throughout Europe.

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Appendix C. Full List of Items Reaching Consensus in Delphi Study

Delphi Method Report

The Delphi Method used in this project aimed to establish the most important items generated from the results of a rapid review about the educational needs and challenges faced by healthcare professionals working in Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs) or those eligible to participate in a MTB. This was achieved by rating the importance of the derived items to reach a consensus.

A total of 93 items were derived from the rapid review, which was step one of the gap analysis conducted in order to identify existing gaps and challenges as previously described, and 15 experts agreed voluntarily to participate in the Delphi process.

Statistical analysis

A comprehensive statistical approach to evaluate consensus among expert participants was applied. We calculated skewness for each item and measured mean or median. A Likert scale from 1-9 was used. To gauge the level of agreement on each item, we calculated the percentage of responses falling within predefined ranges (e.g. 1-3, 4-6, 7-9). These ranges indicated low importance (1-3), medium importance (4-6), and high importance (7-9). This helped us quantify the extent of consensus, particularly focusing on whether a majority (e.g. 75% or more) of responses clustered within a specific range. A percentage of 75% or more was used as a benchmark for strong agreement or consensus. All calculations were executed in Microsoft Excel.

After each round, items that reached consensus were removed and the remaining were used for re-rating in order to reach a consensus. For round 1 we included an open question allowing for the experts to comment on missing items they would like to include for rating or if anything needed to change. In round 2 these items were given for feedback and evaluation. In the final and third round the remaining items were once again rated and final items reaching consensus were derived. Those scoring more or equal to 75% were considered of high importance.

Results are presented for each Delphi round with percentage agreement next to each item.

In the Addendum, visualizations of the vote breakdown per item are presented.

Round 1 Results

In Round 1, 14 experts participated in the rating process.

Round 1 indicated that:

In the Education section:

Please rate the following items regarding the importance of training of healthcare professionals involved or with the potential to be involved in MTBs, based on their importance

- Hereditary cancer, including the difference between germline and somatic tests (75%)
- Genomic testing (83,33%)
- Targeted therapies (91,67%)
- Acquaintance and implementation of tools for interpretation of genomic information (91,67%)
- Informed consent for oncogenomic testing (83,33%)
- Ethical guidelines for oncogenomic testing (75%)
- Research initiatives (75%)
- Communication skills to effectively communicate genetic information to the patients. (83,33%)

In the Communication section:

Please rate the following areas in which training would be beneficial to improve the communication of oncogenomic concepts whether it be with patients or other professionals:

- Explaining complex and sensitive information to patients and families (e.g., preparation before testing (pre-clinic), results of genomic testing, research findings) (83,33%)
- Clarifying genomic concepts and results for multidisciplinary teams (83,33%)
- Promoting interdisciplinary collaboration (83,33%)
- Facilitating family members' and patient communication (83,33%)
- Clarifying requirements to ensure ethical and legal compliance (75%)

In the Clinical Practice and Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs) section:

Please rate the following areas where training in oncogenomics would be beneficial for clinical practice:

- Interpretation of genomic results in real life (e.g., multigene cancer panels) (83,33%)
- Implementation of the latest advances (e.g., new drugs, novel technologies) (83,33%)
- Precision medicine (83,33%)
- Communication skills (e.g., multidisciplinary collaboration, family interactions) (75%)

Please rate the importance of addressing common clinical challenges or complexities that oncology professionals may face regarding genomics:

- Selection of appropriate genetic tests for diagnostics and treatment (75%)
- Clinical utility of genomic diagnostic tests (75%)

Please rate the importance of addressing the following areas of education that might help MTB to operate better:

- Definition of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) (75%)
- Genomic data interpretation (83,33%)
- Awareness of the latest research findings (75%)
- Follow up of cases discussed at MTB (83,33%)
- Leadership and decision-making (75%)
- Awareness of tools that might help in the search of clinical studies available (75%)

- Awareness of off-label treatment availabilities and how to obtain (75%)
- Standardized variants classification (75%)

Please rate the importance of addressing the following topics/situations that may make collaboration and communication with other members of the MTB challenging:

- Varying levels of expertise and knowledge (83,33%)
- Conflicting priorities and responsibilities/lack of availability. (75%)

Advanced, Education section:

Please rate the following items in the predefined fields of knowledge, required as part of the education for MTBs or healthcare professionals that may be evolved in MTBs:

- Defining the genome (75%)
- Defining the transcriptome (75%)
- Difference between whole genome sequencing and targeted next generation sequencing (NGS) panels (75%)
- Defining variants of unknown significance (83,33%)
- Reviewing and understanding a genomic report (83,33%)
- Interpreting genomic and oncogenomic results (83,33%)
- Reviewing a genomic report and identify if further germline testing is indicated (83,33%)
- Identifying treatment options based on a genomic report. (75%)

Advanced, Diagnosis - Hereditary Cancer Syndromes:

- Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of Lynch syndrome (75%)
- Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of hereditary breast and ovarian cancer (75%)
- Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of hereditary colorectal cancer syndromes. (75%)

Advanced, Clinical practice:

- Implementing changes in patient management based on oncogenomic results (75%)
- Using the national guidelines for oncogenomic testing (75%)
- Engaging when participating in MTB meetings (75%)
- Making a shared treatment decision plan with patients (75%)

Advanced, Communication:

- Explaining genomic concepts to patients or caregivers (e.g., somatic genomic test results). (83,33%)

See the Votes Breakdown for Delphi Round 1 in the Addendum for detailed insights.

Round 2 Results

In Round 2, 12 experts participated for the rating process.

Results are as follows:

In the Education section

Please rate the following items regarding the importance of training of healthcare professionals involved or with the potential to be involved in MTBs, based on their importance

- Bioinformatic decision support tools (e.g., OncoKB, Cbioportal, etc) (83,33%)
- Clarifying bioinformatics concepts and tools for multidisciplinary teams (83,33%)

Please rate the importance of addressing the following challenges that may be faced by clinicians when communicating oncogenomics-related information to patients and their families who come from different cultural backgrounds than healthcare professionals':

- Beliefs impacting on understanding and accepting genetic testing (83,33%)
- Low levels of health literacy (83,33%)
- Low levels of genomic literacy (83,33%)

Please rate the following areas where training in oncogenomics would be beneficial for clinical practice:

- Genetic counselling (83,33%)
- Ethical considerations (83,33%)
- Communication skills (e.g., multidisciplinary collaboration, family interactions) (83,33%)

Please rate the importance of addressing common clinical challenges or complexities that oncology professionals may face regarding genomics:

- Selection of appropriate genetic tests for diagnostics and treatment (83,33%)
- Clinical utility of genomic diagnostic tests (75%)
- Costs of testing and reimbursement (75%)
- Lack of established procedures (e.g., referral protocol, limited testing guidelines and protocols) (83,33%)
- Lack of cooperation among the multidisciplinary team members (83,33%)
- Treatment selection based on genomic profiling (83,33%)
- Access to and management of clinical trials (83,33%)

Please rate the importance of addressing the following areas of education that might help MTB to operate better:

- Definition of clear and uniform criteria for patients' enrolment (83,33%)
- Definition of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for selection of molecular test(s) to be proposed (83,33%)
- Awareness of the latest research findings (83,33%)
- Communication and presentation skills (75%)

- Awareness of tools that might help in the search of clinical studies available (75%)
- Awareness of off-label treatment availabilities and how to obtain (83,33%)

Please rate the importance of addressing the following topics/situations that may make collaboration and communication with other members of the MTB challenging:

- Differing interpretation of ONcoKb levels or equivalent measures (75%)
- Lack of standardized protocols and decision-making guidelines (83,33%)
- Differing treatment opinions (83,33%)
- Conflicting priorities and responsibilities/ lack of availability (83,33%)
- Lack of standardized terminology (83,33%)

Advanced, Education

- Defining the exome (75%)
- Difference between whole genome sequencing, whole exome sequencing, RNA sequencing and targeted next generation sequencing (NGS) panels (75%)
- Difference between germline and somatic variants (83,33%)
- Differences between targeted therapy and immunotherapy (83,33%)

Advanced, Diagnosis- Hereditary Cancer Syndromes

- Understanding the oncogenomics aspects of hereditary hematological malignancies (75%)

Advanced, Clinical Practice

- Using oncogenomics (e.g., tumour-based tests) in your daily practice (75%)
- Implementing changes in patient management based on oncogenomic results (75%)
- Engaging when participating in MTB meetings (83,33%)
- Applying the Genetic Non-Discrimination Act (75%)
- Describing the role, indications and limitations of newer technologies (83,33%)
- Accessing the processes for referral to local specialist of clinical genetics service (83,33%)

Advanced, Communication

- Obtaining informed consent to perform genomic testing (75%)
- Communicating germline genomic test results to a patient (75%)
- Communicating germline genomic test results to family members (75%)
- Communicating genomic test results to other professionals (75%)
- Explaining how a result affects the future cancer risk of a patient, and the risks to their relatives (75%)

See the Votes Breakdown for Delphi Round 2 in the Addendum for detailed insights.

Round 3 Results

In Round 3, 10 experts participated for the rating process.

In the Education section:

Please rate the following items regarding the importance of training of healthcare professionals involved or with the potential to be involved in MTBs, based on their importance:

- Tissue sampling (e.g., sampling techniques and tissue handling methods of fixation techniques) (80%)

In the Communication section:

Please rate the importance of addressing common clinical challenges or complexities that oncology professionals may face regarding genomics:

- Inadequate or ineffective communication with diagnosticians (e.g., lab scientists, geneticists) (80%)

Advanced, Diagnosis - Hereditary Cancer Syndromes:

- Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of Multiple Neuroendocrine Neoplasia (80%)
- Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of Lynch syndrome (80%)
- Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of hereditary breast and ovarian cancer (80%)
- Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of hereditary pancreatic cancer (90%)

Advanced, Clinical Practice

- Implementing changes in patient management based on oncogenomic results (75%)
- Engaging when participating in MTB meetings (75%)
- Making a shared treatment decision plan with patients (75%)

Advanced, Communication

- Discussing genomic test results in a multidisciplinary team meeting (75%)

See the Votes Breakdown for Delphi Round 3 in the Addendum for detailed insights.

Aggregate Results per Aggregate Results – Round 1

Aggregate Results – Round

Aggregate Results – Round

Addendum

Votes Breakdown for Delphi Round 1

LOW RANGE		MEDIUM RANGE			HIGH RANGE			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

Stacked bars represent the number of votes for each item in each category separately, e.g. in the Education section for the item «Communication skills to effectively communicate genetic information to the patient» five participants voted 9, three participants voted 8, three participants voted 7, one participant voted 6, one participant voted 5 and one participant voted 2.

In the communication section

Communication of oncogenomic concepts whether it be with patients or other professionals

In the communication section

Communication of oncogenomics-related information to patients and their families who come from different cultural backgrounds than healthcare professionals

In the Clinical practice and Molecular Tumour boards (MTB) section Areas where training in oncogenomics would be beneficial for clinical practice

In the Clinical practice and Molecular Tumour boards (MTB) section The importance of addressing common clinical challenges or complexities that oncology professionals may face regarding genomics

In the Advanced Educational Gaps section

Education

In the Advanced Educational Gaps section

Diagnosis - Hereditary Cancer Syndromes

In the Advanced Educational Gaps section

Clinical Practice

In the Advanced Educational Gaps section

Communication

Votes Breakdown for Delphi Round 2

LOW RANGE

MEDIUM RANGE

HIGH RANGE

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
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Stacked bars represent the number of votes for each item in each category separately, e.g. In the education section, for the item "Bioinformatic decision support tools (e.g., OncoKB, Cbioportal, etc)", two participants voted 9, five participants voted 8, three participants voted 7 and one participant voted 6.

In the communication section
Communication of oncogenomic concepts whether it be with patients or other professionals

In the communication section
Communication of oncogenomics-related information to patients and their families who come from different cultural backgrounds than healthcare professionals

In the Clinical practice and Molecular Tumour boards (MTB) section
Areas where training in oncogenomics would be beneficial for clinical practice

In the Clinical practice and Molecular Tumour boards (MTB) section
The importance of addressing common clinical challenges or complexities that oncology professionals may face regarding genomics

In the Clinical practice and Molecular Tumour boards (MTB) section

Areas of education that might help MTB to operate better

In the Clinical practice and Molecular Tumour boards (MTB) section

Topics/situations that may make collaboration and communication with other members of the MTB challenging

In the Advanced Educational Gaps section

Clinical Practice

In the Advanced Educational Gaps section

Communication

Votes Breakdown for Delphi Round 3

LOW RANGE			MEDIUM RANGE			HIGH RANGE		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

Stacked bars represent the number of votes for each item in each category separately, e.g. in the Education section for the item «Access to and management of clinical trials»: four participants voted 9, two participants voted 8, one participant voted 7, one participant voted 3 and one participant voted 1.

In the Education section

In the communication section
 Communication of oncogenomic concepts whether it be with patients or other professionals

In the communication section
 Communication of oncogenomics-related information to patients and their families who come from different cultural backgrounds than healthcare professionals

In the Clinical practice and Molecular Tumour boards (MTB) section
The importance of addressing common clinical challenges or complexities that oncology
professionals may face regarding genomics

In the Clinical practice and Molecular Tumour boards (MTB) section
Areas of education that might help MTB to operate better

In the Clinical practice and Molecular Tumour boards (MTB) section
 Topics/situations that may make collaboration and communication with other members of the MTB
 challenging

In the Advanced Educational Gaps section

Education

In the Advanced Educational Gaps section

Diagnosis - Hereditary Cancer Syndromes

Appendix D. Survey Questionnaire and Response Summary

Statistics: Survey on the Educational Needs and Challenges of Professionals Working in Oncogenomics

Consent to participate

		Answers	Ratio
Consent		30	88.24 %
No consent		0	0 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Gender

		Answers	Ratio
Male		10	29.41 %
Female		20	58.82 %
Non-binary		0	0 %
Prefer not to reply		0	0 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Age

		Answers	Ratio
29 or younger		2	5.88 %
30-39		6	17.65 %
40-49		10	29.41 %
50 or older		12	35.29 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Location of practice

		Answers	Ratio
Urban		28	82.35 %
Suburb		1	2.94 %
Rural		0	0 %
No Answer		5	14.71 %

Setting of practice

		Answers	Ratio
Academic Hospital		16	47.06 %
Community Hospital		5	14.71 %
Comprehensive Care Center		6	17.65 %
Primary Care		0	0 %
Private Clinic		2	5.88 %
Freelancing		0	0 %
No Answer		7	20.59 %

Expertise status

		Answers	Ratio
Resident (in training)		4	11.76 %
Specialist (qualified)		24	70.59 %
No Answer		6	17.65 %

Professional designation and speciality within oncology (Please tick all that apply)

		Answers	Ratio
Anaesthesiology		0	0 %
Surgery		0	0 %
Radiology		0	0 %
Gynaecology		0	0 %
Nursing		0	0 %
Pharmacy		0	0 %
Haematology		7	20.59 %
Pathology		4	11.76 %
Molecular biology		10	29.41 %
Genetics		16	47.06 %
Biostatistics		2	5.88 %
Computational biology		1	2.94 %
Genetic counselling		6	17.65 %
No Answer		9	26.47 %

Time since completion of residency/specialist training

		Answers	Ratio
Not completed yet		4	11.76 %
5 years or less		4	11.76 %
6 to 10 years		6	17.65 %
11 to 15 years		4	11.76 %
16 or more years		11	32.35 %
No Answer		5	14.71 %

Years of expertise in practising oncology (excluding residency)

		Answers	Ratio
<1 year		3	8.82 %
1 to 3 years		1	2.94 %
3 to 6 years		3	8.82 %
6 or more years		20	58.82 %
No Answer		7	20.59 %

1. How do you keep yourself informed about the latest advancements in genomic testing and targeted therapies?

Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Attending conferences		26	76.47 %
Participating in online fora		9	26.47 %
Reading latest guidelines		26	76.47 %
Reading latest research literature		25	73.53 %
Engaging in continuing education programs		10	29.41 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

2. Which is your preferred training delivery format? Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Online course		14	41.18 %
Formal training (e.g., workshop, university lecture)		17	50 %
Medical and research literature (e.g., self-guided)		18	52.94 %
No Answer		5	14.71 %

3. How often do you use online training tools and web-based resources to find information about cancer genomics topics in which you have limited knowledge of?

		Answers	Ratio
Never (0 times per month)		2	5.88 %
Rarely (1-2 times per month)		6	17.65 %
Sometimes (3-5 times per month)		7	20.59 %
Often (6-8 times per month)		5	14.71 %
Very often (>8 times per month)		9	26.47 %
No Answer		5	14.71 %

4. Have you received any formal training in tissue sampling (e.g., sampling technique and tissue handling methods or fixation techniques?) Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Academic lectures		8	23.53 %
Certificate or specialization programs		3	8.82 %
Workshops, professional conferences or symposia		5	14.71 %
Research initiatives		7	20.59 %
No, I have not received any formal training in this subject		11	32.35 %
No Answer		6	17.65 %

5. Have you received any formal training in education regarding hereditary cancer, including the difference between germline and somatic tests? Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Academic lectures		22	64.71 %
Certificate or specialization programs		11	32.35 %
Workshops, professional conferences or symposia		19	55.88 %
Research initiatives		15	44.12 %
No, I have not received any formal training in this subject		4	11.76 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

6. Have you received any formal training in genomics or oncogenomics (e.g., genomic testing, targeted therapies)?

Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Academic lectures		22	64.71 %
Certificate or specialization programs		12	35.29 %
Workshops, professional conferences or symposia		23	67.65 %
Research initiatives		15	44.12 %
No, I have not received any formal training in this subject		3	8.82 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

7. Have you received any formal training in communication skills to effectively communicate genetic information to your patients? Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Academic lectures		7	20.59 %
Certificate or specialization programs		7	20.59 %
Workshops, professional conferences or symposia		12	35.29 %
Research initiatives		7	20.59 %
No, I have not received any formal training in this subject		13	38.24 %
No Answer		7	20.59 %

8. Please refer any gaps you identify in your education related to your practice in oncogenomics. Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Genomic testing		8	23.53 %
Genetic counselling		7	20.59 %
Pharmacogenomics		19	55.88 %
Targeted therapies		13	38.24 %
Acquaintance and implementation of tools for interpretation of genomic information		16	47.06 %
Informed consent for oncogenomic testing		10	29.41 %
Ethical guidelines for oncogenomic testing		14	41.18 %
No Answer		6	17.65 %

9. From your perspective, what are some significant educational needs or knowledge gaps among fellow oncology professionals? Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Genomic testing		20	58.82 %
Genetic counselling		18	52.94 %
Pharmacogenomics		17	50 %
Targeted therapies		8	23.53 %
Acquaintance and implementation of tools for interpretation of genomic information		20	58.82 %
Informed consent for oncogenomic testing		16	47.06 %
Ethical guidelines for oncogenomic testing		17	50 %
No Answer		6	17.65 %

11. Please identify areas in which training would be beneficial to improve the communication of oncogenomic concepts whether it be with patients or other professionals. Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Explaining complex and sensitive information to patients and families (e.g., preparation before testing (pre-clinic), results of genomic testing, research findings)		16	47.06 %
Clarifying bioinformatics concepts and tools for multidisciplinary teams		19	55.88 %
Clarifying genomic concepts and results for multidisciplinary teams		20	58.82 %
Promoting interdisciplinary collaboration		21	61.76 %
Delivering information to younger groups		8	23.53 %
Facilitating family members' and patient communication		10	29.41 %
Ensuring ethical and legal compliance		15	44.12 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

13. What challenges do you face when communicating oncogenomics-related information to patients and their families who come from different cultural backgrounds than yours? Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Language barriers		10	29.41 %
Beliefs impacting on understanding and accepting genetic testing		6	17.65 %
Low levels of health literacy		6	17.65 %
Low levels of genomic literacy		11	32.35 %
Socioeconomic barriers		5	14.71 %
No Answer		18	52.94 %

14. Please identify the areas in your clinical practice where training in oncogenomics would be beneficial to you. Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Interpretation of genomic results in real-life (e.g., multigene cancer panels)		15	44.12 %
Implementation of the latest advances (e.g., new drugs, novel technologies)		14	41.18 %
Genetic counselling		7	20.59 %
Precision medicine		11	32.35 %
Ethical considerations		9	26.47 %
Communication skills (e.g., multidisciplinary collaboration, family interactions)		10	29.41 %
No Answer		11	32.35 %

15. Based on your experience, what are some common clinical challenges or complexities that oncology professionals face regarding genomics? Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Treatment selection based on genomic profiling		11	32.35 %
Selection of appropriate genetic tests for diagnostics and treatment		18	52.94 %
Clinical utility of genomic diagnostic tests		20	58.82 %
Costs of testing and reimbursement		12	35.29 %
Lack of cooperation among the multidisciplinary team members		11	32.35 %
Inadequate or ineffective communication with diagnosticians (e.g., lab scientists, geneticists)		11	32.35 %
Lack of established procedures (e.g., referral protocol, limited testing guidelines and protocols)		13	38.24 %
No Answer		9	26.47 %

b) please identify areas of education that might help MTB to operate better. Please choose all that apply:

		Answers	Ratio
Definition of clear and uniform criteria for patients' enrolment		13	38.24 %
Definition of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for selection of molecular test(s) to be proposed		11	32.35 %
Genomic data interpretation		13	38.24 %
Ethical considerations		7	20.59 %
Awareness of the latest research findings		14	41.18 %
Follow up of cases discussed at MTB		15	44.12 %
Leadership and decision-making		6	17.65 %
Communication and presentation skills		6	17.65 %
Awareness of tools that might help in the search of clinical studies available		14	41.18 %
Awareness of off-label treatment availabilities and how to obtain		10	29.41 %
Standardized variants classification		12	35.29 %
No Answer		11	32.35 %

Education : 17. Defining the genome

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		1	2.94 %
Moderate		3	8.82 %
Good		12	35.29 %
Excellent		13	38.24 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		1	2.94 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 18. Defining the exome

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		2	5.88 %
Moderate		2	5.88 %
Good		12	35.29 %
Excellent		13	38.24 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		1	2.94 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 19. Defining the transcriptome

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		3	8.82 %
Moderate		4	11.76 %
Good		9	26.47 %
Excellent		12	35.29 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		2	5.88 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 20. Difference between whole genome sequencing, whole exome sequencing, RNA sequencing and targeted next generation sequencing (NGS) panels

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		3	8.82 %
Moderate		3	8.82 %
Good		6	17.65 %
Excellent		17	50 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		1	2.94 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 21. Difference between germline and somatic variants

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		1	2.94 %
Moderate		0	0 %
Good		10	29.41 %
Excellent		18	52.94 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		1	2.94 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 22. Defining variants of unknown significance

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		4	11.76 %
Moderate		5	14.71 %
Good		8	23.53 %
Excellent		12	35.29 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		1	2.94 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 23. Reviewing and understanding a genomic report

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		0	0 %
Moderate		7	20.59 %
Good		11	32.35 %
Excellent		11	32.35 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		1	2.94 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 24. Interpreting genomic and oncogenomic results

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		1	2.94 %
Moderate		8	23.53 %
Good		12	35.29 %
Excellent		8	23.53 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		1	2.94 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 25. Reviewing a genomic report and identify if further germline testing is indicated

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		2	5.88 %
Moderate		5	14.71 %
Good		13	38.24 %
Excellent		8	23.53 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		2	5.88 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 26. Identifying treatment options based on a genomic report

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		0	0 %
Moderate		10	29.41 %
Good		9	26.47 %
Excellent		3	8.82 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		8	23.53 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 27. Differences between targeted therapy and immunotherapy

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		1	2.94 %
Moderate		2	5.88 %
Good		8	23.53 %
Excellent		15	44.12 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		3	8.82 %
No Answer		5	14.71 %

Education : 28. Understanding pre-implantation genetic diagnosis (PGD) procedures as a reproductive option for BRCA

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		5	14.71 %
Moderate		9	26.47 %
Good		3	8.82 %
Excellent		6	17.65 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		7	20.59 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 29. Familiarity with the polygenic risk score (PRS)

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		7	20.59 %
Moderate		9	26.47 %
Good		10	29.41 %
Excellent		4	11.76 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		0	0 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Education : 30. Risk-reducing bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy (RRBSO) in high-risk women

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		9	26.47 %
Moderate		2	5.88 %
Good		5	14.71 %
Excellent		7	20.59 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		6	17.65 %
No Answer		5	14.71 %

Diagnoses – Hereditary Cancer Syndromes : 31. Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of Multiple Neuroendocrine Neoplasia

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		9	26.47 %
Moderate		7	20.59 %
Good		6	17.65 %
Excellent		6	17.65 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		2	5.88 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Diagnoses – Hereditary Cancer Syndromes : 32. Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of Li- Fraumeni syndrome

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		4	11.76 %
Moderate		7	20.59 %
Good		8	23.53 %
Excellent		9	26.47 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		2	5.88 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Diagnoses – Hereditary Cancer Syndromes : 33. Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of Von Hippel- Lindau disease

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		5	14.71 %
Moderate		10	29.41 %
Good		6	17.65 %
Excellent		7	20.59 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		2	5.88 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Diagnoses – Hereditary Cancer Syndromes : 34. Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of Lynch syndrome

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		3	8.82 %
Moderate		5	14.71 %
Good		8	23.53 %
Excellent		13	38.24 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		1	2.94 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Diagnoses – Hereditary Cancer Syndromes : 35. Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of hereditary breast and ovarian cancer

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		2	5.88 %
Moderate		7	20.59 %
Good		9	26.47 %
Excellent		10	29.41 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		1	2.94 %
No Answer		5	14.71 %

Diagnoses – Hereditary Cancer Syndromes : 36. Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of hereditary pancreatic cancer

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		5	14.71 %
Moderate		7	20.59 %
Good		10	29.41 %
Excellent		6	17.65 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		2	5.88 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Diagnoses – Hereditary Cancer Syndromes : 37. Understanding the oncogenomic aspects of hereditary colorectal cancer syndromes

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		3	8.82 %
Moderate		6	17.65 %
Good		9	26.47 %
Excellent		10	29.41 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		2	5.88 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Diagnoses – Hereditary Cancer Syndromes : 38. Understanding the oncogenomics aspects of hereditary hematological malignancies

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		7	20.59 %
Moderate		9	26.47 %
Good		4	11.76 %
Excellent		6	17.65 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		4	11.76 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Clinical Practice : 39. Using oncogenomics (e.g., tumour-based tests) in your daily practice

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		1	2.94 %
Moderate		3	8.82 %
Good		11	32.35 %
Excellent		7	20.59 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		8	23.53 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Clinical Practice : 40. Implementing changes in patient management based on oncogenomic results

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		0	0 %
Moderate		4	11.76 %
Good		5	14.71 %
Excellent		3	8.82 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		17	50 %
No Answer		5	14.71 %

Clinical Practice : 41. Using the national guidelines for oncogenomic testing

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		1	2.94 %
Moderate		3	8.82 %
Good		9	26.47 %
Excellent		6	17.65 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		9	26.47 %
No Answer		6	17.65 %

Clinical Practice : 42. Engaging when participating in MTB meetings

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		3	8.82 %
Moderate		2	5.88 %
Good		7	20.59 %
Excellent		8	23.53 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		10	29.41 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Clinical Practice : 43. Applying the Genetic Non-Discrimination Act

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		5	14.71 %
Moderate		2	5.88 %
Good		1	2.94 %
Excellent		5	14.71 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		14	41.18 %
No Answer		7	20.59 %

Clinical Practice : 44. Describing the role, indications and limitations of newer technologies

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		2	5.88 %
Moderate		8	23.53 %
Good		8	23.53 %
Excellent		5	14.71 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		7	20.59 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Clinical Practice : 45. Accessing the processes for referral to local specialist of clinical genetics service

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		3	8.82 %
Moderate		6	17.65 %
Good		4	11.76 %
Excellent		4	11.76 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		13	38.24 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Clinical Practice : 46. Making a shared treatment decision plan with patients

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		1	2.94 %
Moderate		2	5.88 %
Good		6	17.65 %
Excellent		3	8.82 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		17	50 %
No Answer		5	14.71 %

Communication : 47. Discussing genomic test results in a multidisciplinary team meeting

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		1	2.94 %
Moderate		6	17.65 %
Good		11	32.35 %
Excellent		9	26.47 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		2	5.88 %
No Answer		5	14.71 %

Communication : 48. Discussing oncogenomics in your daily practice

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		2	5.88 %
Moderate		1	2.94 %
Good		15	44.12 %
Excellent		9	26.47 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		3	8.82 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Communication : 49. Explaining genomic concepts to patients or caregivers (e.g., somatic genomic test results)

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		1	2.94 %
Moderate		1	2.94 %
Good		13	38.24 %
Excellent		7	20.59 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		8	23.53 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Communication : 50. Obtaining informed consent to perform genomic testing

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		1	2.94 %
Moderate		2	5.88 %
Good		7	20.59 %
Excellent		7	20.59 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		13	38.24 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Communication : 51. Communicating germline genomic test results to a patient

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		2	5.88 %
Moderate		3	8.82 %
Good		5	14.71 %
Excellent		6	17.65 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		14	41.18 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Communication : 52. Communicating germline genomic test results to family members

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		2	5.88 %
Moderate		3	8.82 %
Good		5	14.71 %
Excellent		6	17.65 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		14	41.18 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Communication : 53. Communicating genomic test results to other professionals

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		0	0 %
Moderate		4	11.76 %
Good		11	32.35 %
Excellent		10	29.41 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		5	14.71 %
No Answer		4	11.76 %

Communication : 54. Explaining how a result affects the future cancer risk of a patient, and the risks to their relatives

		Answers	Ratio
Limited		0	0 %
Moderate		6	17.65 %
Good		9	26.47 %
Excellent		6	17.65 %
N/A due to the nature of the profession		8	23.53 %
No Answer		5	14.71 %